

1 Table S1. *Phylogenetic Signal Quantification Using Abouheif's Cmean after PCA de-*
 2 *composition. Due to software limitations only 44 dimensions considered in PCA. Each*
 3 *row is the average of the 44 traits of all 5 runs. Results reported with 95% confidence*
 4 *intervals, using a student's t-distribution. Best results in bold. Results within confidence*
 5 *interval of the best score are underlined.*

Dataset Split	Loss Function	Average Cmean		Maximum Cmean		p value < 0.05 with Cmean		
		Cmean	p value	Cmean	p value	> 0.3	> 0.5	> 0.7
Clade	Arcface	-0.022 ± 0.023	0.537 ± 0.048	0.608	0.001	5%	1%	0.0%
Clade	Contra	-0.021 ± 0.028	0.505 ± 0.051	0.661	0.085	5%	2%	0.0%
Clade	Margin06d	-0.025 ± 0.023	0.543 ± 0.049	0.632	0.002	5%	0%	0.0%
Clade	Multisim	-0.02 ± 0.027	0.546 ± 0.047	0.788	0.007	6%	4%	1.8%
Clade	Proxy	-0.021 ± 0.023	0.542 ± 0.048	0.537	0.023	7%	1%	0.0%
Clade	Tripd	-0.022 ± 0.026	0.560 ± 0.048	0.746	0.001	7%	3%	0.9%
Stratified	Arcface	-0.024 ± 0.015	0.501 ± 0.041	0.282	0.417	0%	0%	0.0%
Stratified	Contra	-0.02 ± 0.032	0.517 ± 0.055	0.582	0.001	11%	2%	0.0%
Stratified	Margin06d	-0.021 ± 0.024	0.538 ± 0.050	0.598	0.004	5%	0%	0.0%
Stratified	Multisim	-0.022 ± 0.024	0.540 ± 0.049	0.493	0.113	5%	0%	0.0%
Stratified	Proxy	-0.024 ± 0.016	0.522 ± 0.042	0.328	0.321	0%	0%	0.0%
Stratified	Tripd	-0.019 ± 0.027	0.566 ± 0.050	0.705	0.001	8%	3%	0.5%